

INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR:

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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Effect of Herbal Extracts on the Survival of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Goats' Raw Milk Cheese

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Abstract

Previous work from our research group showed that lemon balm, sage and spearmint hydroethanolic extracts possess antimicrobial capacities. Thus, this work aimed to evaluate the antimicrobial effect of these herbal extracts against *S. aureus* in goat's raw milk cheeses during maturation, which have shown moderate prevalence of this pathogen.

Lyophilised herbal extracts were produced using ethanol 70% (v/v) in a shaking water bath. Milk was inoculated with *S. aureus* ($-5 \log$ CFU/g) and 1% (w/w) of each extract was added to the curd, while a non-inoculated control was kept. Maturation occurred at 10°C and 98% RH for 15 days. *S. aureus* counts and pH were determined at specific days. For every treatment, a log-decay function with tail in differential form (with varying D-value), coupled to a Bigelow equation of D-value as a function of pH (with parameters $\log D_{ref}$ at pH 7.0 and z_{pH}) was adjusted.

The models adequately fitted the survival curves, with RMSE of 0.116, 0.063 and 0.057 for spearmint, lemon balm and sage respectively, producing significant parameter estimates ($p < 0.05$). $\log D_{ref}$ was affected by the addition of extracts (spearmint: 0.621 ± 0.061 ; lemon balm: 1.189 ± 0.200 ; sage: 0.996 ± 0.278) in comparison to the controls (0.932 ± 0.166 ; 0.996 ± 0.056 ; 0.796 ± 0.068 , respectively). z_{pH} was higher with the addition of spearmint (3.172 ± 0.660), whereas sage (2.006 ± 0.677) and lemon balm (2.339 ± 0.835), did not affect z_{pH} . Overall, the addition of extracts significantly decreased the time to achieve one log reduction. This work characterises *S. aureus* survival parameters in goat's milk cheeses and demonstrates the utility of these biopreservatives against *S. aureus* during cheese maturation.

Keywords: Log-decay model; Bigelow model; D-value; z; dairy

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